

IMPORTANT INDICATORS OF DEVELOPMENT OF ECONOMIC COMPETENCIES IN STUDENTS.

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Abstract: This article provides analytical information about important indicators of the development of economic competence in students, integral and non-standard approaches to the formation of personnel competences, in-depth analysis of adequacy and interference situations in the process of determining future competences.

Keywords: personnel competencies, integral and non-standard approach, determinism, adequacy and interference cases, professional and personal competencies, indicator, mathematical competence.

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Today, the superiority of the integral and non-standard approach to the formation of the competences of the personnel being trained all over the world is clearly visible. It is acknowledged by influential international experts that the traditional approach to the training of professional personnel is not effective enough, and in this regard, determining the role and importance of professional and personal competencies, determining the level of determinants of knowledge and skills in relation to the demands and needs of the changing labor market is recognized as the main task of today's pedagogy.

Especially in the process of determining the future competencies, experts have a difficult task of in-depth analysis of adequacy and interference situations, forming a list of dominant competencies of priority importance, and clearly defining the indicators that create the abilities and talents of young people based on an innovative approach.

In the last three years, economic growth has been observed in our republic as a result of socio-economic changes. These processes put the task of training a new generation of personnel for Uzbekistan, which is being renewed, in front of HEIs. In the "Concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the following are listed among the existing problems in the field of ensuring the quality of education in the higher education system:

➤ current qualification requirements, curricula and programs are not oriented to the formation of practical skills in graduates in terms of content;

- the work on personnel training in mutual cooperation with higher education institutions and personnel contractors has not been effectively launched,
- the participation of employers in the formation of the content of higher education is insufficient; students have not developed the skills of critical thinking, independent information search and analysis;
- practical training in production enterprises is not effectively organized, the qualification level of trained specialists does not sufficiently meet the modern requirements of the labor market.

One of the conditions that ensure the elimination of the identified problems is the improvement of the quality of education based on an integrative approach.

Raising the process of training of economic personnel to a new level in terms of quality, its competitiveness in the labor market depends on many factors, including the mathematical education of the specialist. In today's conditions, the integration of mathematical education in the preparation of highly qualified economists who competently apply mathematical knowledge in their professional activities is not fully developed from a theoretical and methodological point of view, including the weakness of issues of interdisciplinary communication and practical orientation in mathematical education; lack of cooperation between mathematicians and pedagogues of specialist training departments.

The need for future economists to have mathematical knowledge aimed at solving problems related to their professional activities is related to the need to form the mathematical competence of an economist.

Competence does not mean the acquisition of separate knowledge and skills by the student, but the acquisition of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent direction. In terms of the requirements for the level of professional training of students, competence means the ability of students to use a set of knowledge, skills and methods of activity appropriately in certain situations.

In our opinion, the mathematical competence of future economists can be considered as a central component of his professional competence. Therefore, the concept of "mathematical competence" of an economist is the result of integrative, dynamically developing education of a specialist, which reflects the integrity of theoretical mathematical training and the ability to competently apply mathematical methods to solve professional and economic problems. Creativity is an important indicator of the development of economic competence in students. There are different approaches to the interpretation of the concept of "creative ability". Students' creativity is formed by their innovative approaches to their work.

Creativity is characterized by initiative, effective communication, high political and social status, developed foresight intuition and quick perception of the direction of organizational activity. The essence of creativity is that intelligence is

the mental potential of a person, and creativity is the ability to freely use this mental potential in a purposeful manner.

The term creativity appeared in Anglo-American psychology in the 60s. It means the ability of an individual to create new concepts and new skills.

Creativity requires creative and innovative approaches to their activities from modern educational managers. From this point of view, creative thinking fulfills the most important tasks of managing the educational process of students in the modern world.

Leadership of the mind is the ability to come up with not one, but several solutions to problems that most people don't have time to think about in a given time frame, and to justify the unique pros and cons of each.

The flexibility of thinking is the realization that the template directions and principles accepted in society and traditionally existing, which are actually thought to be correct, are no longer able to respond to modern development, to perceive new directions and measures, to be able to think and formulate them, to be able to rebuild one's activities and solve problems in a new way. is to be able to mobilize oneself in the directions.

Prognosis, and the ability to predict, is the thinking of precognition of the nature of future changes in the development of one's field, the causes of origin, and the periods of occurrence through mental analysis. For example, increases and decreases in labor productivity, changes in business conditions or markets and the impact of these changes on the industry, increases and decreases in prices, etc.

It is considered possible to educate the leadership and flexibility of the mind in creative thinking of students on the basis of special abstract exercises and knowledge. Creative thinking refers to the selection and development of completely new methods, ways, and tools that are goal-oriented, but not previously known and not traditionally experienced.

In modern management, a certain system representing the practice of creative thinking has been formed, which can be explained as follows:

- challenge your thinking to find original solutions and promote them, force yourself to develop new ideas;
- don't be afraid that other people will get the wrong idea about you;
- to observe widely, use non-traditional methods, try to get out of the shell of your own way of thinking, national mentality and stereotypes;
- even if your first experiment is unsuccessful, do not give up your experiments, continue to think in unconventional ways, find other options for solving the problem, continue to search for other ways;
- always be open to discussion and debate, do not believe that the debate is aimed at you, organize the debate correctly, control your thoughts during the debate;
- try to understand the essence of incomprehensible and incomprehensible things and events.

It is known that one of the problems of higher education at present is: on the one hand, the need to take into account the individual characteristics of students, and on the other hand, the lack of possibility to implement individualization of teaching within the traditional educational process.

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